

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Review Article

**PHARMACOLOGICAL AND TOXICOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF
HELIOTROPIUM UNDULATUM [H. BACCIFERUM] AND
HELIOTROPIUM EUROPAEUM- A REVIEW**

Ali Esmail Al-Snafi

Department of Pharmacology, College of Medicine, University of Thi qar, Iraq.
Cell: +9647801397994. E mail: aboahmad61@yahoo.com**Abstract:**

The phytochemical analysis of Heliotropium undulatum [Heliotropium bacciferum] revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, and phenols. While, Heliotropium europaeum was shown to contain three major alkaloids: heliotrine N-oxide 0.08%, lasiocarpine 0.09% and lasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%; and four minor alkaloids: heliotrine 0.02%, europine 0.02%, acetylasiocarpine 0.03% and a novel alkaloid acetylasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%. Twenty six compounds were identified in the essential oil of Heliotropium europaeum. The previous pharmacological studies showed that these species possessed antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and hepatoprotective effects. However, pyrrolizidine alkaloids were toxic for animals and human. This review was designed to highlight the chemical constituents, pharmacological and toxic effects of Heliotropium undulatum [Heliotropium bacciferum] and Heliotropium europaeum.

Keywords: chemical constituents, pharmacology, toxicology, Heliotropium undulatum, Heliotropium bacciferum, Heliotropium europaeum

Corresponding author:**Ali Esmail Al-Snafi**

Department of Pharmacology,

College of Medicine,

University of Thi qar, Iraq

Cell: +9647801397994.

E mail: aboahmad61@yahoo.com

QR code

Please cite this article in press Ali Esmail Al-Snafi., *Pharmacological and Toxicological Effects of Heliotropium Undulatum [H. Bacciferum] and Heliotropium Europaeum- A Review*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(04).

INTRODUCTION:

Plants are a valuable source of a wide range of secondary metabolites, which are used as pharmaceuticals, agrochemicals, flavours, fragrances, colours, biopesticides and food additives [1-20]. The phytochemical analysis of *Heliotropium undulatum* [*Heliotropium bacciferum*] revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, and phenols. While, *Heliotropium europaeum* was shown to contain three major alkaloids: heliotrine N-oxide 0.08%, lasiocarpine 0.09% and lasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%; and four minor alkaloids: heliotrine 0.02%, europine 0.02%, acetylasiocarpine 0.03% and a novel alkaloid acetylasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%. Twenty six compounds were identified in the essential oil of *Heliotropium europaeum*. The previous pharmacological studies showed that these species possessed antioxidant, antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory and **hepatoprotective** effects. However, pyrrolizidine alkaloids were toxic for animals and human. This review was designed to highlight the chemical constituents, pharmacological and toxic effects of *Heliotropium undulatum* [*Heliotropium bacciferum*] and *Heliotropium europaeum*.

Plant profiles:**Synonyms:*****Heliotropium undulatum*:**

H. bacciferum Forssk., *H. affghanum* Boiss, *H. arenarium* F. Muell., *H. eriocarpum* Delile ex Lehm., *H. nubicum* Bunge, *Sericostoma arenarium* [Vatke] IM Johnst and *Dialion undulatum*[21].

***Heliotropium europaeum*:**

H. album St.-Lag., *H. commutatum* Schult., *H. dioscoridis* Bubani, *H. glandulosum* R. Br., *H. gymnocarpum* Borbás, *H. lacunarium* F. Muell., *H. subcanescens* Steven and *H. vulgare* Gaterau [21].

Taxonomic classification:

Kingdom: Plantae, **Subkingdom:** Viridiplantae, **Infra kingdom:** Streptophyta, **Superdivision:** Embryophyta, **Division:** Tracheophyta, **Subdivision:** Spermatophytina, **Class:** Magnoliopsida, **Superorder:** Asteranae, **Order:** Boraginales, **Family:** Heliotropiaceae, **Genus:** *Heliotropium*, **Species:** *Heliotropium undulatum* and *Heliotropium europaeum*[22-23].

Common names:***Heliotropium undulatum*:**

Arabic: Ramram Zerraij, Thanb Al Agrab, Hâbaliya, Hbâilia[24].

***Heliotropium europaeum*:**

Arabic: Tanoom, Karee, Tafeen, Aqrabana, I'jairbeh, Hashishat Al Agrab; **English:** Barooga-weed, Caterpillar-weed, Common heliotrope, European heliotrope, European turnsole, Heliotrope, Hemp-agrimony, Wandarric-curse, Wild heliotrope; **French:** Héliotrope d'Europe; **German:** Europäische Sonnenwende, Sonnenwende; **Iran:** Aftab parast, Akreer; **Italy:** Eliotropio, Commune, Erba porraja; **Portuguese:** Heliotrópio-europeu; **Spanish:** Verrucaria; **Swedish:** Ogråsheliotrop; **Turkey:** Akrep out, Bambul out[25-26].

Distribution:***Heliotropium undulatum*:**

Heliotropium undulatum was distributed in Bahrain, Egypt, Iran, Iraq Palestine, Jordania, Kuwait, Oman, Saudi Arabia, United Arab Emirates, Yemen, Afghanistan, Pakistan, Libya, Morocco, Algeria, Tunisia, Mauritania, Mali, Chad, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Somalia, Sudan, Senegal, Comoros, Madagascar, India and Australia[27].

***Heliotropium europaeum*:**

Heliotropium europaeum was reported to be native to southern and central Europe, northern Africa, and western Asia. Now, it presents in Africa [Algeria, Egypt, Libya, Morocco, Tunisia]; Asia: [Afghanistan, China, India, Pakistan, Indonesia, Iran, Iraq, Palestine, Jordan, Lebanon, Oman, Saudi Arabia, Syria, Turkey, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan, Armenia, Georgia, Russian Federation]; Europe [Moldova, Russian Federation-European part, Ukraine, Austria, Czech Republic, Germany, Hungary, Slovakia, Switzerland, Albania, Bulgaria, Croatia, Greece, Italy, Romania, Serbia, Slovenia]; Australasia [Australia] and Northern America [United States][25-26].

Description:***Heliotropium undulatum*:**

Perennial, decumbent or procumbent with a woody base, short and stout up to 15 mm thick at base. Leaves lanceolate to linear-lanceolate, 5-55 x 2-16 mm, flat or terete, hairy on both surfaces, margin revolute, longer hairs stiff, up to 2 mm long, arising from bulbous base. Inflorescence reduced, up to 20 mm long, bearing close set uniseriate flowers. Calyx persistent, 2-2.5 mm long, 5-partite into lanceolate lobes, hairy to the outside; hairs often stiff and arising from a bulbous base. Corolla white, c. 2.5-3 mm long; tube shortly cylindrical, hairy outside, glabrous within; lobes imbricate, 0.7-0.8 mm long, oblong to suborbicular, crenulate to undulate. Anthers 1-1.2

mm long, elongate, broader at base, attached c. 1.1 mm from the corolla base, slightly furrowed and sometimes 2-fid at apex. Style shorter than stigma. Fruit globose, usually hairy when young; nutlets 4, brown, margin winged, back rugulose, sometimes with a membranous inflated back[28-29].

Heliotropium europaeum:

Herbs annual, 20-50 cm tall. Stems erect or ascending, branched from base, strigose or hirtellous. Petiole 1-4 cm; leaf blade elliptic to elliptic-ovate, 1.5-4 × 1-2.5 cm, abaxially gray-green and densely hirtellous, adaxially green and sparsely hirtellous, base widely cuneate to rounded, apex obtuse to acute. Cymes terminal and axillary, scorpioid, simple or dichotomously branched, 2-4 cm. Flowers sessile. Calyx lobes ovate to ovate-lanceolate, 2-3 × 1-1.5 mm, not enlarged in fruit, strigose. Corolla white, 4-5 mm, base 1.5-2 mm wide; throat slightly contracted; limb [2-]3-4 mm wide; lobes rounded, ca. 1.5 mm wide, short strigose outside, glabrous inside. Anthers ovate-oblong, ca. 1 mm, without filaments, attached ca. 1 mm above base of corolla tube. Ovary globose, 0.5-0.7 mm in diam. Style short; stigma long conical, deeply 2-cleft, 1.2-1.5 mm, ringlike portion glabrous, apex short strigose. Fruit 2.5-3 mm in diam.; mericarps ovate, ca. 2 mm, ± distinctly tuberculate, glabrous[30]

Traditional uses:

Heliotropium undulatum [H. bacciferum]:

Heliotropium bacciferum was used for hypotension, fever and stomach ulcers in traditional medicine[31]. It was used in Cape Verde as a cardiogenic. It was also used as a repellent for storage insects in Egypt and Pakistan[32].

Heliotropium europaeum:

It was used as purifier. Flowers were used to give relief from constipation and piles. Powder of leaves was used to treat skin problems[33].

The juice of the crushed *Heliotropium europaeum* was used topically to treat dermatophytosis of hair, nails and skin in domestic animals, while boiled leaves were applied on skin to treat pimples and eruption[34-36]

Part used:

Flowers and leaves[33].

Physicochemical characteristics:

Heliotropium undulatum:

Extractive value of the leaves in methanol, n-hexan, ethyl acetate, n-Butanol and aqueous were 32.64 ± 0.02, 14.76 ± 0.03, 15.83 ± 0.02, 16.43 ± 0.04 and 23.79 ± 0.05%, extractive value of the stems were 18.13 ± 0.05, 12.46 ± 0.01, 13.89 ± 0.03, 14.13 ±

0.10 and 20.10 ± 0.03% and that of roots were 13.10 ± 0.08, 10.32 ± 0.03, 12.70 ± 0.06, 11.34 ± 0.12 and 17.16 ± 0.08% respectively. Moisture value of the leaves was 11.36 ± 0.04% and Ash value of the whole plant was 8.67 ± 0.06 % [37].

Chemical constituents:

Heliotropium undulatum [H. bacciferum]:

Phytochemical analysis of crude and fractions of the plant revealed the presence of alkaloids, saponins, tannins, steroids, terpenoids, flavonoids, glycosides, and phenols[37].

Alkanes, alkenes, alkyl halides, amines, carboxylic acids, amides, esters, alcohols, phenols, nitrocompounds, and aromatic compounds were identified from the extracts of *Heliotropium bacciferum*[38].

Four pyrrolizidine alkaloids [heleurine, heliotrine, supinine, and europine] were isolated from *Heliotropium bacciferum*[39].

Quantitative analysis of fatty acids of *Heliotropium bacciferum* by GC-MS analysis revealed the presence of linoleic acid 65.70%, eicosadienoic acid 15.12%, oleic acid 8.72%, palmitic acid 8.14%, stearic acid 1.74%, elaidic acid 0.58% and myristic acid 0.20% [37].

Heliotropium europaeum:

Twenty six compounds were identified in the essential oil of *Heliotropium europaeum* represented 91.4% of the total essential oil. The identified compounds and their percent were: *trans*-linalool oxide 1.6%, *cis*- linalool oxide 1.8%, eugenol 1.6%, β- longipinene 1%, geranyl acetone 6.3%, [*E*]- β-ionone 4.8%, *n*-tridecanol 1.9%, silphiperfol-6-en-5-one 7.1%, alloaromadendriene epoxide 3.8%, β-eudesmol 0.7%, *n*-tetradecanol 2.4%, eudesma-7[11]-en-4-ol 0.6%, *E*-coniferyl alcohol 1.1%, α-oxobisabolene 0.3%, *n*-pentadecanol 2.6%, β-eudesmol acetate 1.2%, *n*-hexadecanol 1.8%, phytol 28.7%, *n*-octadecanol 3.2%, *Cis*- linoleic acid methyl ester 7.3%, *n*-heneicosane 3.2%, phytol acetate 4.3%, *n*- pentacosane 0.9%, *n*- hexacosane 0.8%, *n*-heptacosan 1.3%e and *n*- octacosane 1.1% [40].

The pyrrolizidine alkaloids isolated from the aerial plant parts of *Heliotropium europaeum* were included: supinine-type 2.3 ± 0.4 µg/g dry [included: supinine, supinine-N-oxide, heleurine, heleurine-N-oxide]; Heliotrine-type 80.0 ± 7.9 µg/g dry weight [included: heliotrine, europine, heliotrine-N-oxide, europine-N-oxide, rinderine, 5'-hydroxyrinderine, 3'-acetylinderine, rinderine-N-oxide, 5'-hydroxyrinderine-N-oxide, 3'-

acetylriinderine-N-oxide, 5'-acetyeuropine, 5'-acetyeuropine-N-oxide, echinatine-N-oxide]; and Lasiocarpine-type 28.7 ± 2.2 $\mu\text{g/g}$ dry weight [included: 7-angeloylheliotrine-N-oxide, lasiocarpine, lasiocarpine-N-oxide, *iso*-lasiocarpine, *iso*-lasiocarpine-N-oxide, 5'-acetylasiocarpine, 5'-acetylasiocarpine-N-oxide, *iso*-acetylasiocarpine, *iso*-acetylasiocarpine-N-oxide, heliosupine, 3'-acetylheliosupine, heliosupine-N-oxide and 3'-acetylheliosupine-N-oxide][41].

The total pyrrolizidine alkaloid and tertiary base content of the seeds of *Heliotropium europaeum* were found to be 0.28 % and 0.02 % respectively. Higher percentage of alkaloids were present as N-oxides [92.86 % of the alkaloids]. Alkaloids found in the tertiary base fraction and total alkaloid fraction were identified as europine 14.27%, heliotrine 2.44%, supinine 9.09%, heleurine 2.65%, lasiocarpine 8.69% and 7-angeloylheliotrine 2.86%[42-43].

Heliotropium europaeum population Garmsar was shown to contain three major alkaloids: heliotrine N-oxide 0.08%, lasiocarpine 0.09% and lasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%; and four minor alkaloids: heliotrine 0.02%, europine 0.02%, acetylasiocarpine 0.03% and a novel alkaloid acetylasiocarpine N-oxide 0.05%[44].

Alkaloid, heliotridine esterified on the methylol hydroxyl with lasiocarpic acid [2,3-dihydroxy-4-methoxy-2-methylpentane-3-carboxylic acid], supinine [supinidine esterified with trachelanthic acid], supinidine esterified with heliotric acid [3-hydroxy-4-methoxy-2-methylpentane-3-carboxylic acid], N-oxides of heliotrine and lasiocarpine were isolated from *Heliotropium europaeum*[43]

Pharmacological effects:

Antioxidant effect:

The leaves, stem, and roots extracts of *Heliotropium bacciferum* exhibited significant DPPH radical scavenging activities. The plant leaves extracts revealed excellent DPPH radical scavenging activities ranging from 52.59 ± 0.84 to 90.74 ± 1.00 at concentrations of 50, 100, 150, 200, and 250 mg/ml[37].

The antioxidant effect of *Heliotropium bacciferum* flower extracts was investigated against 2, 2-diphenyl-1-picryl hydrazyl radical. Extracts displayed noteworthy radical scavenging activities at all concentrations [25–225 $\mu\text{g/ml}$]. Notable activities were recorded by crude, chloroform and ethyl acetate extracts up to 88.27% at 225 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ concentration[38].

Antimicrobial effect:

The antimicrobial activity of *Heliotropium europaeum* oil [250, 500, 1000, 2000, 4000 and 8000 $\mu\text{g/ disk}$] was investigated against *Bacillus subtilis* PTCC 1023, *Staphylococcus aureus* PTCC 1112, *Escherichia coli* PTCC 1330, *Salmonella typhi* PTCC 1639, *Aspergillus niger* PTCC 5011 and *Candida albicans* PTCC 5027. The diameter of zone of growth inhibition was 12, 12.5 and 15.75mm against *Bacillus subtilis* and 11.75, 12.5 12mm against *Salmonella typhi* at concentration of 2000, 4000 and 8000 $\mu\text{g/ disk}$ respectively. However it showed weak activity against *Escherichia coli* and *Aspergillus niger*, and no activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Candida albicans*[40].

The antimicrobial effects of leaves, flowers, and stem extracts of *Heliotropium bacciferum* were against seven bacterial species [*Escherichia coli* [ATCC 25922], *Staphylococcus aureus* [ATCC 6538], *Bacillus cereus* [ATCC 7722], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [ATCC 9721], *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [ATCC 6824], *Proteus mirabilis* [ATCC 7103], and *Erwinia carotovora* [ATCC 8452]] and five fungal strains [*Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus parasiticus*, *Aspergillus oryzae*, and *Aspergillus fumigates*]. All extracts exhibit a range antibacterial effects. Methanol, *n*-hexane, and ethyl acetate extracts of plant leaves [15 μg] revealed significant activities [18 ± 0.46 mm, 20 ± 0.71 mm, and 21 ± 0.69 mm] against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Staphylococcus aureus* [16 ± 0.51 mm, 17 ± 0.34 mm, and 19 ± 0.53 mm], *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [16 ± 0.44 mm, 17 ± 0.58 mm, and 15 ± 0.53 mm], and *Escherichia coli* [13 ± 0.32 mm, 19 ± 0.46 mm, and 18 ± 0.65 mm], respectively. Plant leaves chloroform and *n*-butanol extracts [15 μg] were active against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* [16 ± 0.37 mm and 14 ± 0.75 mm] and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [17 ± 0.73 mm and 10 ± 0.28 mm]. Plant flowers *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, and *n*-butanol extracts [15 μg] showed prominent activities against *Escherichia coli* [17 ± 0.46 mm, 16 ± 0.64 mm, and 14 ± 0.34 mm], *Staphylococcus aureus* [19 ± 0.76 mm, 20 ± 0.74 mm, and 11 ± 0.54 mm], and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* [19 ± 0.75 mm, 19 ± 0.48 mm, and 13 ± 0.46 mm], respectively. Chloroform and *n*-butanol extracts [15 μg] of plant stem showed noteworthy activities [15 ± 0.53 mm and 11 ± 0.43 mm] against *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumonia* [17 ± 0.56 mm and 15 ± 0.64 mm], respectively. Aqueous extracts [15 μg] of plant stem were active against *Klebsiella pneumoniae*

[13 ± 0.42 mm], *Proteus mirabilis* [10 ± 0.29 mm], and *Erwinia carotovora* [11 ± 0.26 mm]. Ethyl acetate and *n*-hexane extracts [15 µg] of plant stem were active against all bacterial microorganisms. Methanol, *n*-hexane, chloroform, ethyl acetate, and *n*-butanol extracts [15 µg] of leaves showed prominent activities against *Aspergillus niger* [17 ± 0.44 mm, 14 ± 0.52 mm, 12 ± 0.28 mm, 15 ± 0.43 mm, and 11 ± 0.43 mm], *Aspergillus flavus* [15 ± 0.38 mm, 17 ± 0.67 mm, 13 ± 0.53 mm, 17 ± 0.32 mm, and 14 ± 0.51 mm], and *Aspergillus oryzae* [11 ± 0.54 mm, 16 ± 0.68 mm, 16 ± 0.45 mm, 17 ± 0.83 mm, and 15 ± 0.57 mm], respectively. Methanol, chloroform, and *n*-butanol extracts [15 µg] of flowers revealed noteworthy activities against *Aspergillus niger* [14 ± 0.25 mm, 11 ± 0.26 mm, and 13 ± 0.47 mm] and *Aspergillus flavus* [17 ± 0.63 mm, 14 ± 0.46 mm, and 11 ± 0.23 mm], respectively. Significant activities were recorded by *n*-hexane and ethyl acetate extracts of plant flowers against *Aspergillus niger* [17 ± 0.63 mm and 16 ± 0.59 mm], *Aspergillus flavus* [15 ± 0.48 mm, 15 ± 0.59 mm], and *Aspergillus oryzae* [12 ± 0.27 mm and 15 ± 0.44 mm], respectively. Methanol and chloroform extracts [15 µg] of plant stem were active against *Aspergillus niger* [16 ± 0.54 mm and 15 ± 0.54 mm] and *Aspergillus fumigatus* [15 ± 0.51 mm and 14 ± 0.37 mm], respectively. Excellent activities were shown by *n*-hexane and ethyl acetate extracts [15 µg] against *Aspergillus flavus* [11 ± 0.31 mm and 18 ± 0.50 mm], *Aspergillus oryzae* [17 ± 0.54 mm and 15 ± 0.55 mm], and *Aspergillus fumigatus* [12 ± 0.33 mm and 16 ± 0.54 mm], respectively[38].

The crude [methanol fraction] and *n*-hexane, ethyl acetate, butanol and aqueous fractions of *Heliotropium bacciferum* were subjected to antibacterial and antifungal activities against bacterial isolates: *Salmonella typhi*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas Aeruginosa*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Erwinia carotovora*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Bacillus subtilis*, *Bacillus atrophaeus*, and fungal isolates: *Trichoderma longibrachiantum*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus niger*, *Fusarium solani* and *Candida albican*. All the fractions were active against different bacterial strains but *n*-hexane and ethyl acetate showed [zone of inhibition ranged from 18-30 mm] highest activity. Excellent inhibitory effect was observed against all fungal strains. The minimum inhibitory concentrations [MICs] of the investigated plant fractions ranged from 0.5- 2.00 mg/ml[45].

The antibacterial effects of *Heliotropium bacciferum* aerial parts extracts and chloroform, ethyl acetate and aqueous fractions, were evaluated against five

bacterial strains. *H. bacciferum* extracts exhibited a significant activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E.coli* and *Salmonella enteritidis*. MICs were ranged between 7.6 and 125 µg/ml. Among the extracts, the aqueous extract showed the most antibacterial[31, 46].

Hepatoprotective effect:

The hepatoprotective effect of *n*-butanol extract of *Heliotropium undulatum* [HUBE] was evaluated in acetylhydrazide [ACHD] induced hepatotoxicity in rats. Hepatic damage was induced by administration of ACHD [300 mg/Kg op]. HUBE [200 mg/Kg, op] administered for 14 days before ACHD administration, caused a decrease in LPO levels and in the transaminase and ALP levels and restored the GSH and its related enzymes [GPx, GST, GR] [50-62 %]. Simultaneous administration of HUBE afforded a partial protection in hepatic GSH[47]

Antiinflammatory effect:

The anti-inflammatory effect of extracts of 17 plant genera were studied using the carrageenan induced inflammation in rats' paws. The plant extracts were obtained using methanol and dichloromethane as solvent and administered intraperitoneally at the concentration of 2g/kg bw. Dichloromethane extract of the aerial parts of *Heliotropium bacciferum* caused 28.2±3.1% inhibition of edema volume, 2 hours after injection of carrageenan[48].

Pyrrolizidine alkaloids poisoning:

Pyrrolizidine alkaloids poisoning of livestock caused by the accidental ingestion of feed contaminated with *Heliotropium* spp, was common worldwide. The most common toxic pyrrolizidine alkaloids found in *Heliotropium* were mono- or di- esters of C1-C2 unsaturated necine bases [1,2-dehydro PAs] of the supinidine-type, heliotridine-type, and retronecine-type[49-51].

Cattle were more susceptible than sheep, while horses were the most susceptible. Pyrrolizidine alkaloids - poisoning in livestock was clinically characterized by staggering, tremor, tenesmus and sudden death, the latter usually occurs several weeks up to several months from the time of exposure. Macroscopically, the livers were pale and firm, histopathological feature characterized by proliferation of bile-duct epithelial cells, megalocytosis, veno-occlusive lesions, nodular regeneration and fibrosis[52-54]

A herd of 15-18 months old mixed breed beef cattle [n=73] from the Galilee region in Palestine, was accidentally fed hay contaminated with 12% *Heliotropium europaeum* [average total PA intake was 33 mg PA/kg BW/d]. After 42 day of feed, sudden death occurred over a time period of 63 day

with a mortality rate of 33%. Necropsy and histopathological examination revealed fibrotic livers, moderate ascites, as well as various degrees of bile duct epithelial cells hyperplasia and fibrosis. Elevated γ -glutamyl-transferase and alkaline phosphatase levels were indicative of severe liver damage[41, 55].

Most sheep fed for prolonged periods on a ration containing 50% dried *Heliotropium europaeum* developed some of the clinical manifestations seen in field cases of pyrrolizidine alkaloidosis. Histologically demonstrated liver damage was comparatively mild, but the marked decline in their bromosulphophthalein [BSP] clearance rates indicated severe depletion of liver functional capacity. In sheep fed on *Heliotropium europaeum* for 13 wk periods separated by 18 weeks rests, simultaneous oral administration of iodoform [16 mg twice daily] led to an increase from 33-55 weeks in the time required for death of half the susceptible sheep. All susceptible sheep not given iodoform died following 2 periods of *Heliotropium europaeum* feeding, while 3 such periods were needed for iodoform-treated animals. Iodoform prophylaxis may be a useful protective measure in the field for sheep exposed to *Heliotropium europaeum* grazing during a single season. Up to 20% of the sheep used survived ingestion of *Heliotropium europaeum* for the full experimental term and some sustained little or no decline in BSP clearance rate[56-59].

In a field experiment, ewes and wethers grazed *Heliotropium europaeum* over periods of 3 to 4 months in 4 successive years. 12% [14 of 120] of the sheep had died by the end of the second year; after 4 years the loss attributable to *Heliotropium europaeum* was between 18% and 35%. Mortality was not affected by intraruminal treatment with cobalt or antimethanogen. At the end of the experiment the highest concentration of copper in the liver was 1.95 mmol/kg wet weight [approximately 413 micrograms/g dry weight][60].

The disease produced by feeding chickens and ducks a commercial poultry feed containing heliotrine and lasiocarpine [pyrrolizidine alkaloids of *Heliotropium europaeum*], was studied. Ascites, ill thrif and degenerative lesions in the liver were the major findings. Similar lesions were occurred in chickens fed a diet containing *Heliotropium europaeum* [61].

Human poisoning with pyrrolizidine alkaloids was usually accidental, caused most commonly by the

ingestion of grain contaminated with pyrrolizidine containing weeds and using of herbs for medicinal purposes. Pyrrolizidine alkaloid poisoning in humans were recorded in South Africa, Jamaica, USSR and Tadjikistan. To date the largest reported outbreak of human intoxication by pyrrolizidine alkaloid was in Afghanistan in 1974 when an estimated 35000 people were affected after grain was contaminated with *Heliotropium* plant material. Among 7200 cases examined, 1600 were affected and many died 3-9 months after the onset of clinical signs[62-67].

In acute cases there were sudden attacks of abdominal pain, vomiting, ascites occurred in 96%, hepatomegaly in 85%, with marked increase in liver enzymes in 92% of patients. Liver biopsies during the acute stage showed collagenous occlusion of the small branches of the hepatic venous tree with dilated sinusoids forming collaterals in the parenchyma, massive centrilobular congestion and centrilobular necrosis [veno-occlusive liver disease]. Subacute cases characterized by ascites, persistent hepatomegaly, small vein occlusion, and surrounding fibrosis. Symptoms include abdominal pain, diarrhea, vomiting, and abdominal swelling with the development of collateral venous channels over the abdomen. Chronic cases characterized by progressive ascites and signs of portal hypertension. Histologically there were fibrosis and inflammatory infiltration of the portal tracts, giving rise to a picture of cirrhosis. Complete recovery may occurred in limited lesions, but extensive lesions may caused hepatic failure leading to death[68-73].

Side effects:

The possible toxic effects of water extract of *H. bacciferum* on the reproductive system was investigated in rats. Histological examinations revealed no changes in the tissues of the testes, although, some changes were detected in the cauda epididymis, the most important of which was the development of small lesions of spermatic granulomas[74].

The effect of ethanol extracts of *Heliotropium europaeum* [orally at 3 dose levels; 100, 200 and 400 mg/kg for a period of 7 weeks] on reproductive organs and fertility was studied in male rats. Sperm motility, count, viability and morphology and serum levels of testosterone, follicle stimulating hormone [FSH], leutinizing hormone [LH] and prolactin were

assessed. Percentage of mating and fertility success and fertility index were also calculated. The testes, liver and kidney were processed for histological examination. The effect on biochemical parameters

like aspartate aminotransferase [AST], alanine aminotransferase [ALT], urea, and creatinine were estimated. Hematological profiles such as red blood cell [RBC] count, total leucocyte count [TLC], hemoglobin [Hb] concentration and packed cell volume [PCV] were quantified. The results showed that the ethanol extract of *Heliotropium europaeum* possesses potential fertility lowering effects without altering general body metabolism[34].

CONCLUSION:

This review discussed the chemical constituents, pharmacological and toxic effects of *Heliotropium undulatum* [*Heliotropium bacciferum*] and *Heliotropium europaeum*.

REFERENCES:

- Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Echium italicum*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 394-398.
- Al-Snafi AE. Therapeutic importance of *Ephedra alata* and *Ephedra foliata*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 399-406.
- Al-Snafi AE. Therapeutic potential of *Erodium cicutarium* - A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 407-413.
- Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Fraxinus ornus*- A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1721-1727.
- Al-Snafi AE. *Fumaria parviflora*- A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1728-1738.
- Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and medical importance of *Galium aparine* - A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1739-1744.
- Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacological effects of *Helianthus annuus*- A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]:1745-1756.
- Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Hypericum triquetrifolium*. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1757-1765.
- Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological and therapeutic effects of *Jasminum sambac*- A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1766-1778.
- Al-Snafi AE. Medical importance of *Juniperus communis* - A review. Indo Am J P Sc 2018; 5[3]: 1979-1792.
- Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Desmostachya bipinnata*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 60-66.
- Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents and pharmacological effects of *Eryngium creticum*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 67-73.
- Al-Snafi AE. A review on *Erodium cicutarium*: A potential medicinal plant. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 110-116.
- Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacology of *Echinochloa crus-galli* - A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 117-122.
- Al-Snafi AE. The pharmacological potential of *Dactyloctenium aegyptium*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 153-159.
- Al-Snafi AE. Chemical constituents, pharmacological and therapeutic effects of *Eupatorium cannabinum*- A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[1]: 160-168.
- Al-Snafi AE. Phytochemical constituents and medicinal properties of *Digitalis lanata* and *Digitalis purpurea* - A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 225-234.
- Al-Snafi AE. Therapeutic and biological activities of *Daphne mucronata* - A review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 235-240.
- Al-Snafi AE. Pharmacological and therapeutic importance of *Erigeron canadensis* [Syn: *Conyza canadensis*]. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 248-256.
- Al-Snafi AE. *Eschscholzia californica*: A phytochemical and pharmacological review. Indo Am J P Sci 2017; 4[2]: 257-263.
- The plant list, a working list of all plant species, *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk., <http://www.theplantlist.org/tpl/record/kew-2843806>
- ITIS, *Heliotropium europaeum*, https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=31645#null
- IT IS, *Heliotropium undulatum*, https://www.itis.gov/servlet/SingleRpt/SingleRpt?search_topic=TSN&search_value=514624#null
- Globel plants, *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk. http://plants.jstor.org/stable/10.5555/al.ap.upwta.1_585
- U.S. National Plant Germplasm System, *Heliotropium europaeum*, <https://npgsweb.ars-grin.gov/gringlobal/taxonomydetail.aspx?18823>
- Invasive Species Compendium, *Heliotropium europaeum* [common heliotrope], <http://www.cabi.org/isc/datasheet/26898>
- Catalogue of Life: *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forsk, <http://www.Catalogueoflife.org/col/details/pecies/id/ac66906746411a4f71259d952a3a9df2> [29 May 2017].
- Flora of Pakistan, *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk., http://www.efloras.org/florataxon.aspx?flora_id=5&taxon_id=250069117
- Globel plants, *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk. <http://plants.jstor.org/compilation/heliotropium.bacciferum>
- Flora of China, *Heliotropium europaeum* http://www.efloras.org/florataxon.aspx?flora_id=2&taxon_id=200019032

31. Rahimifard N, Bagheri E, Asgarpanah G, Balajadeh BK and Yazdi HR. Antibacterial activity of total extract, petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and aqueous fractions of aerial parts of *Heliotropium bacciferum*. JPM 2014; 4[52]: 122-135.
32. PROTA4U, *Heliotropium ramosissimum* [Lehm.] DC., www.prota4u.org/ database/protav8.asp?g=pe&p=Heliotropium+ramosissimum+[Lehm.]+DC.
33. Mahmood A, Qureshi RA, Mahmood A, Sangi Y, Shaheen H, Ahmad I and Nawaz Z. Ethnobotanical survey of common medicinal plants used by people of district Mirpur, AJK, Pakistan. Journal of Medicinal Plants Research 2011; 5[18]: 4493-4498.
34. Yusufoglu H, Soliman GA, Abdel-Rahman RF, Al Qasumi SI, Anul SA, Akaydin G and Tatli II. . Evaluating the antifertility potential of the ethanolic extracts of *Heliotropium europaeum* and *Taraxacum serotinum* in male rats. FABAD J Pharm Sci 2013; 38[1]: 11-23.
35. Bonet M and Valle's J. Ethnobotany of montseny biosphere reserve [Catalonia, Iberian Peninsula]: Plants used in veterinary medicine. J Ethnopharmacol 2007; 110: 130-147.
36. Qureshi R, Bhatti R and Memon R. Ethnomedical uses of herbs from northern part of Nora desert, Pakistan. Pak J Bot 2010; 42: 839-851.
37. Ahmad S, Ahmad S, Ahtaram Bibi A *et al*, . Phytochemical analysis, antioxidant activity, fatty acids composition, and functional group analysis of *Heliotropium bacciferum*. Scientific World Journal 2014; 2014: 829076. doi: 10.1155/2014/829076
38. Ahmad S, Abd El-Salam NM and Ullah R. *In vitro* antimicrobial bioassays, DPPH radical scavenging activity, and FTIR spectroscopy analysis of *Heliotropium bacciferum*. Biomed Res Int 2016; 2016: 3818945. doi:10.1155/2016/3818945
39. Farrag NM, Abdel-Aziz EM, El-Shafae AM and El Domiaty MM. Pyrrolizidine alkaloids of *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk. from Egypt. International Journal of Pharmacognosy 1996; 34[5]:374-377.
40. Saeedi M and Morteza-Semnani K. Chemical composition and antimicrobial activity of essential oil of *Heliotropium europaeum*. Chemistry of Natural Compounds 2009; 45[1]: 98-99.
41. Shimshoni JA, Mulder PPJ, Bouznach A, Ederly N, Pasval I, Barel S, Abd-El Khaliq M and Perl S. *Heliotropium europaeum* poisoning in cattle and analysis of its pyrrolizidine alkaloid profile. J Agric Food Chem 2015; 63 [5]: 1664–1672.
42. Tosun F and Tamer U. Determination of pyrrolizidine alkaloid in the seeds of *Heliotropium europaeum* By GC-MS. Ankara Ecz Fak Derg [J Fac Pharm Ankara] 2004; 33[1]:7-9.
43. Culvenor CCJ. Alkaloids of *Heliotropium europaeum*. II Isolation and structures of the third major alkaloid and two minor alkaloids and isolations of the principal Noxides. Aust J Chem 1954; 7[3]: 287-297.
44. Yassa N, Farsam H, Rustaiyan A and Shafiee A. Alkaloids of boraginaceae II [1], pyrrolizidine alkaloids of *Heliotropium europaeum* L. Population Garmsar. Journal of Science, Islamic Republic of Iran 1999; 10: 39-42.
45. Ahmad S, Ahmad S, Bibi I, AbdEl-Salam NM, Hussain H, Ishaq MS, AdnanM, Tariq A and Ullah R. Antibacterial and antifungal activities of the extract and fractions of aerial parts of *Heliotropium bacciferum*. African Journal of Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medicines 2015; 12[2]:32–35.
46. Rahimifard N, Bagheri E, Asgarpanah J, Balajadeh BK, Yazdi H and Bagheri F. Study of the antibacterial activity of total extract and petroleum ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate and aqueous fractions of aerial parts of *Heliotropium bacciferum* against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Bacillus cereus*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *E. coli*, *Salmonella enteritidis*. Biosciences Biotechnology Res Asia 2014; 11[1]: 239-248.
47. Ameddah S, Deffa O, Aissaoui H, Menad A, Mekkiou R, Benayache F and Benayache S. Influence of *Heliotropium undulatum* on hepatic glutathione conjugating enzymes system in acetylhydrazide-rats. ICPPP 2016: 18th International Conference on Pharmacology, Pharmacoevidence and Pharmacovigilance, Istanbul, Turkey. April 19-20, 2016, International Scholarly and Scientific Research & Innovation 3[4] 2016, <https://waset.org/abstracts/40515>
48. Mohammed MS, Khalid HS, Muddathir AE, El Tahir K, Khan AA, Abd Algadir H, Osman WJA and Siddiqui NA. Effect of some plants' extracts used in Sudanese folkloric medicines on carrageenan-induced inflammation. Pak J Pharm Sci 2015; 28[1]:159-165.
49. El-Shazly A and Wink M. Diversity of pyrrolizidine alkaloids in the Boraginaceae structures, distribution and biological properties. Diversity 2014; 6: 188-282.

50. Rizk AM. Naturally occurring pyrrolizidine alkaloids. CRC Press, Boca Raton, FL, 1991: 234, 462
51. EFSA Panel on Contaminants in the Food Chain [CONTAM]; Scientific Opinion on pyrrolizidine alkaloids in food and feed. EFSA Journal 2011; 9[11]:2406. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2011.2406.
52. Molyneux RJ, Johnson EA and Stuart LD. Delayed manifestation of Senecio-induced pyrrolizidine alkaloidosis in cattle: case reports. Vet Hum Toxicol 1988; 30: 201-205.
53. Craig AM, Pearson EG, Meyer C and Schmitz JA. Serum liver enzyme and histopathologic changes in calves with chronic and chronic-delayed Senecio jacobaea toxicosis. Am J Vet Res 1991; 52: 1969-1978.
54. Shlosberg A, Egyed MN, Nobel TA, Klopfer U, Perl S and Yakobson B. First cases in Israel of chronic poisoning in calves caused by ingestion of *Heliotropium europaeum*. Refuah Vet 1981; 38: 80-88.
55. Hill BD, Gaul KL and Noble JW. Poisoning of feedlot cattle by seeds of *Heliotropium europaeum*. Aust Vet J 1997; 75[5]: 360-361.
56. Lanigan GW, Payne AL and Peterson JE. Anti methanogenic drugs and *Heliotropium europaeum* poisoning in penned sheep. Australian Journal of Agricultural Research 1978; 29[6]:1281-1292.
57. Caple IW and Heath TJ. Effect of chronic liver damage caused by ingestion of *Heliotropium europaeum* on bile formation in sheep. J Comp Pathol 1979; 89[1]: 83-88.
58. Lanigan GW and Whittam JH. Cobalt pellets and *Heliotropium europaeum* poisoning in penned sheep. Aust Vet J 1970; 46[1]:17-21.
59. Hunt ER. Hepatotoxicity of carbon tetrachloride in sheep. 2. Influence of ingestion of *Heliotropium europaeum*. Aust Vet J 1972;48[2]:57-61.
60. Peterson JE, Payne A and Culvenor CC. *Heliotropium europaeum* poisoning of sheep with low liver copper concentrations and the preventive efficacy of cobalt and antimethanogen. Aust Vet J 1992; 69[3]: 51-56.
61. Pass DA, Hogg GG, Russell RG, Edgar JA, Tence IM and Rikard-Bell L. Poisoning of chickens and ducks by pyrrolizidine alkaloids of *Heliotropium europaeum*. Aust Vet J 1979; 55[6]: 284-288.
62. Willmot FC and Robertson GW. Senecio disease or cirrhosis of the liver due to *Senecio* poisoning. Lancet 1920; 2:848-849.
63. Stuart KL and Bras G. Venous-occlusive disease of the liver. QJM 1957; 26:291-315.
64. Bras G, Brooks S and Walter D. Cirrhosis of the liver in Jamaica. J Pathol Bacteriol 1961;82:503-512.
65. Savvina K. Pathological anatomy of atrophic hepatic cirrhosis. Arkhiv Patologii 1952; 14:65-70.
66. Braginski B and Bobokhadzaev H. Hepatosplenomegaly against the background of heliotropic toxicosis. Sov Med 1965; 28:57-60.
67. Mohabbat O, Younis MS, Merzad AA, et al. An outbreak of hepatic veno-occlusive disease in North-Western Afghanistan. Lancet 1976; ii:269-271.
68. Steenkamp V, Stewart M and Zuckerman M. Clinical and analytical aspects of pyrrolizidine poisoning caused by South African traditional medicines. Ther Drug Monit 2000; 22:302-306.
69. Freiman I, Schmaman A, Zamit R, et al. Venous-occlusive disease of the liver—some new aspects. S Afr Med J 1968; 42:126-129.
70. Sperl W, Stuppner H, Gassner I, et al. Reversible hepatic venoocclusive disease in an infant after consumption of pyrrolizidine containing herbal tea. Eur J Pediatr 1995;154:112-116.
71. McLean E. The toxic actions of pyrrolizidine [Senecio] alkaloids. Pharmacol Rev 1970;22:429-483.
72. Selzer G and Parker R. Senecio poisoning exhibiting as Chiari's syndrome. Am J Pathol 1951; 27:885-907.
73. Rose EF. Senecio species: toxic plants used as food and medicine in Transkei. S Afr Med J 1972;46:1039-1043.
74. Alanazi K, Alahmadi BA, Alhimaidi A, Abou-Tarboush FM, Abul Farah M, Mahmoud A and Alfaifi M. Development of spermatocytic granuloma in albino rats following administration of water extract of *Heliotropium bacciferum* Forssk. Saudi J Biol Sci 2016; 23[1]: 87-91.